

Argiope were reared, Spiders are highly cannibalistic and readily devour one another when other prey is not available. This behavior is a mechanism

that regulates their number.

We conclude that rice agroecosystems are rich in species of natural enemies that attack BPH. The apparent lack of

hyperparasites in the Philippines is an encouraging indication that natural enemies can be directly manipulated. ■

Yield loss due to leaf scald disease

S. Srinivasan. Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Leaf scald disease was initially observed in the 1977 samba season in Tanjore district, Tamil Nadu. During the 1978 thaladi season, the disease was seen in all

cultivars raised. In the 1979 thaladi the disease incidence was severe (up to grade 8) in the culture AS2887. Yield losses were assessed. For each disease grade, 100 uniform clumps were harvested and the yield was recorded. The yield loss was worked out in comparison with the yield obtained in 100 healthy clumps of the same variety. The particulars on the

percentage loss in the yield is given below.

Disease grade	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
% yield loss	-	-	-	-	2.5	7.9	16.1	23.4

Leaf scald disease up to grade 4 caused no yield loss in AS2887; loss was maximum, 23.4%, at disease grade 8. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Efficacy of chlorpyrifos (Coroban) 5 & 10 G against two major rice pests in Tamil Nadu

A. Abdul Kareem and T. Visvanathan, Entomology Department, Coromandel Indag Products (CIP) Research Farm, Padappai 601301 Tamil Nadu, India

A field trial on control of leaf roller *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* and stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, major rice pests in Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, with the rice variety Ponni was conducted by the entomology department at CIP (P) LTD Research Farm during the 1979-80 samba season (Oct-Jan). The study evaluated the efficacy of chlorpyrifos (Coroban) as 5 and 10 G formulated in the chemistry department of the Farm.

Five treatments, each on a 20-m² plot, were replicated 4 times. The granules were broadcast into 2.5-cm paddy water 10 days after transplanting (DT). Chlorpyrifos (Coroban 20 EC) at 500 ml/ha was foliar sprayed twice at 3-week intervals, starting 40 DT to all treatments including the check.

Observations of the cumulative incidence of leaf rollers (leaf damage) and stem borers (deadhearts) were made at 2-week intervals. Grain yields were also recorded.

Chlorpyrifos granules 5 and 10 G were as effective as carbofuran 3 G and quinalphos 5 G against the two pests (see

Relative efficacy of chlorpyrifos 5 and 10 G against rice leaf rollers and yellow stem borers. CIP Research Farm, Tamil Nadu, India. ^a

Insecticide	Leaf roller incidence ^b		Stem borer deadhearts (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	15 DT	30 DT	15 DT	30 DT	
Chlorpyrifos 5 G	2.5 a	1.8 a	3 a	8 b	4.45 ab
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.5 a	3.8 b	2 a	5 ab	4.85 a
Quinalphos 5 G	2.5 a	4.0 b	11 b	5 ab	4.40 ab
Carbofuran 3 G	2.8 a	2.8 ab	6 a	3 a	4.15 b
Control	14.0 b	15.3 c	14 b	16 c	2.85 c

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DT = days after transplanting. ^bNumber of damaged leaves in 10 randomly selected and marked hills.

table). All insecticide treatments yielded significantly more than the control. The highest grain yields from plots treated

with chlorpyrifos 10 G were significantly greater than yields from plots treated with carbofuran. ■

Studies on a new insecticide of a novel class of chemical thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate for the control of rice insects

Chih-Chen Shang, Institute of Elemento-Organic Chemistry, Nankai University Tienjin, China; and Shin-Foon Chiu, Plant Protection Department, South China Agricultural College, Kwangchow (Canton) China

In China, a large quantity of insecticides are used annually for control of rice insect pests. Most of these insecticides are γ -BHC and methyl parathion. Because of the development of resistance by rice stem borers and other species to these organochlorine and organophosphate chemicals and because

of residue hazards to the environment, it has become necessary to search for insecticides of different structures and action.

Results of laboratory and field experiments (1977-79) showed that thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (Evisect) developed in China from an annelid worm is effective as a spray or root-zone application against striped stem borer, the yellow stem borer, the leaf folder, and rice thrips. Evisect has systemic properties. When used in combination with carbofuran it can control most of the potential insect pests in rice fields.

Another related insecticide, dimehypo (S, S[dimethylamine] trimethylene dithiosulfuric acid ester, is also being evaluated in China. ■